

INTERNAL COMBUSTION ENGINE I HEATING FURNACE AND DEVELOPMENT OF REQUIREMENTS FOR IT.

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[doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.11234503](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11234503)

The main goal of this work is to prepare technologies for further improvement of the heating system in a modern internal combustion engine and meet the requirements set for them, and form the requirements. While the changes in modern heating system technology may not be visible in day-to-day service, the fact is that automakers continue to change heating system performance to improve fuel economy and power output.

Modern heating systems mainly use engine coolant to heat the cabin, with its help it is heated and filtered atmospheric air. A fan is used for forced air intake. The air is heated by the heat transfer of a working car engine, the intensity of its supply is regulated manually or automatically.

A normally functioning car heater, which drivers simply call a "stove", warms the air in the cabin to 20-25 degrees Celsius in winter. An additional function of the car heater is to heat the fogged or frosted windows of the car, to melt the frozen windshield wipers.

Development of the heating system: The stationary heating system of a car with an internal combustion engine (diesel or gasoline) uses the working heat of the engine as a heat source. For most heating systems, an air intake fan and a heat exchanger (stove radiator) are installed in front of the engine compartment compartment. . The heater is connected to the cooling system of the car engine through the outlet and inlet pipes. Atmospheric air blown by the fan heats up as it passes through the radiator cells. After that, the heated air passes through the cabin filter and is supplied through the pipes to the cabin ventilation deflectors . Deflectors for different models of cars are located on the center console, in the center and on the sides of the instrument panel, under the windshield, and can come out from under the feet of the rear passengers. The normal temperature of the engine operating at 90 degrees provides heating of the air supplied to the cabin to 30-35 degrees. An important quality of the heating system is the regulation of the supply of hot air. The power of the air supply is regulated by turning the knob or pressing the button with the fan icon (for air conditioning systems). Manual adjustment of the air direction to the sides of the deflector shock absorbers is very approximate. Climate control is much more precise. After the driver sets the desired temperature on the on-board computer, the climate control unit automatically adjusts

the opening or closing of the shock absorbers using temperature sensors through servomotors. can use ri and rotation modes. Circulation mode works with the main air intake damper closed. In this case, the exhaust fan of the heating system uses only the volume of air from the passenger compartment. At the same time, the air temperature rises, the unpleasant smells of road dust and car emissions disappear in the cabin. The recirculation mode works most effectively in automatic climate control devices. Taking into account the indicators of gas analyzers, the climate control unit automatically turns on the circulation mode when harmful substances are detected in the atmospheric air. Also, if the amount of carbon dioxide in the cabin rises from the breath of passengers, the circulation mode is automatically turned off.

Autonomous internal heaters: In addition to the functions of heating when the engine is turned on, in some cases it is necessary to provide preheating of the passenger compartment and heating of the engine. For this, autonomous heaters and front heaters are installed in trucks and cars. Webasto, Eberspacher, the Russian brand Planar stand out among the quality manufacturers of autonomous heaters. Despite the distrust of car owners in autonomous heaters, the advantages of such a device are clear. When using it, the engine does not need to be idle, which allows you to significantly save fuel. Using the remote activation of the autonomous heater, the driver sits behind the wheel in a warm cabin with clean windows and ready-to-use "switches". Reduces engine wear by eliminating cold starts with cooled oil.

the engine heating system includes:

- flushing the cooling system and the start-up heating boiler;
- heating and cooling systems, troubleshooting;
- check the operation of the thermostat, the condition and operation of the radiator shutter;
- checking the operation of the starting heater and other auxiliary means to facilitate engine start-up, troubleshooting;

Electronic thermostats: Although originally introduced on high-end imports, one of the two types of electronic thermostats will undoubtedly be found in our future vehicles. The first type is basically a conventional thermostat, which opens by electrically heating the surrounding cooling water.

The second type is a new design in which the opening of the thermostat is directly electronically controlled. In either case, the powertrain control module (PCM) uses these types of thermostats to regulate engine temperature to match the requirements of part-throttle and wide-open throttle operation.

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